

Studies in Terpenes. Part XV. The Action of Maleic Anhydride on (+)-Limonene

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(+)-Limonene does not react with maleic anhydride under mild conditions. At temperatures above 75° or in acetone medium, it gives rise to one or more of the following products: terpinolene, α -terpinene and its maleic anhydride adduct, *p*-cymene, and succinic anhydride, depending on the conditions of the reaction.

Whereas Hultzsch¹ found that the reaction of (+)-limonene (I) with maleic anhydride afforded limononylsuccinic anhydride (II), Alder and Schmidt² claimed that the adduct formation furnished the anhydride (III) derived from the isomeric 3,8 (9)-*p*-menthadiene. A careful reinvestigation of Alder and Schmidt's reaction by Eschinazi and Pinos³ showed, however, that (+)-limonene did not respond to maleic anhydride. In view of these conflicting results, we decided to examine the transformations of (+)-limonene with maleic anhydride in greater detail.

(I)

(II)

(III)

TABLE I

Reaction of (+)-limonene with maleic anhydride.

Reaction.	(+)-Limonene**.	Maleic anhydride.	Solvent.	Temp.	Reaction time.	Steam distillate.	Ref. No.	
a*	4.2 g.	0.031M	6.10g.	0.062M	Nil	20-30°	96 hr.	4.5
b†	100.0	0.735	25.0	0.166	Benzene	105-108°	3	155.00
					80 ml			
c‡	50.4	0.370	72.5	0.740	Nil	75° ± 2°	2	42.80
d*	50.4	0.370	72.5	0.740	Nil	75° ± 2°	3	38.80
e*	50.4	0.370	72.5	0.740	Nil	75° ± 2°	6	24.70
f*	42.0	0.310	60.8	0.620	Acetone	33°	1	37.80
					100 ml			
g*†	27.2	0.200	19.6	0.200	Nil	155-270°	6	3.60
h*†	27.2	0.200	19.6	0.200	Nil	155-270°	3	3.40

1. *Ber.*, 1939, 72, 1173.

2. *Annalen*, 1949, 565, 118.

3. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 1666.

**Kindly donated by Minute Maid Corp., Plymouth, Florida. The purified sample had b.p. 175-76°/740mm, n_D^{20} 1.4728, [α] $_D^{20}$ +120°.

*Closed flask.

†In presence of 0.2 g. of hydroquinone.

‡Reflex condenser attached.

§The crude adduct on pyrolysis afforded *p*-cymene and succinic anhydride.

TABLE II
Analytical data of steam-volatile reaction products¹.

No.	Reaction: Wt. of oil fractionated (g.): Pressure (mm):	b ^a		c ^b		d ³		e ³		f ³		g ³		h ⁴	
		Yield.	n _D ²⁰ .												
1	160-66°	0.85	1.4850	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	1.70 g.	1.4690	1.10 g.	1.4720
2	166-71°	0.85	1.4830	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	2.60	1.4724	2.20	1.4754
3	171-73°	0.70	1.4727	*1.85 g.	1.4712	*1.30 g.	1.4715	*3.00 g.	1.4694	*2.50 g.	1.4676	*2.20	1.4764	*1.20	1.4806
4	173-75°	0.85	1.4725	*1.40	1.4702	*3.10	1.4705	*2.60	1.4706	*2.30	1.4701	*6.20	1.4804	*2.30	1.4812
5	175-78°	*99.00	1.4728	*16.70	1.4724	*16.20	1.4716	*11.60	1.4730	*15.90	1.4721	2.20	1.4844	3.60	1.4822
6	178-81°	..	..	*3.10	1.4764	*2.10	1.4762	..	..	*3.00	1.4772	..	..	..	..
7	181-88°	..	..	*2.60	1.4884	*1.70	1.4862	..	..	*1.60	1.4881	..	..	..	..
8	Residue steam distilled	*3.00	1.4750	*1.20	1.4884	*1.00	1.4892	*1.30	1.4864	*1.00	1.4884	1.70	1.4966	*1.30	1.4948
	% p-Cymene in steam distillate	Nil	1.8	1.8	2.6	3.9	1.8	46.3	25.4						

¹The steam distillate of reaction (e) was identified to be unchanged (+)-limonene by means of b.p., refractive index, and infrared spectrum.

²Fractionation in Todd assembly with 90 cm/12 mm column, pyrex brand glass helices packing, reflux ratio 25:1.

³Fractionation with 90 cm/5mm column, Monel spiral packing, reflux ratio 23:1.

⁴Fractionation with 90cm/5mm column, Monel spiral packing, reflux ratio 50:1.

⁵Preceded by 52.2 g. of benzene at 80°.

Compounds identified ¹chemically in the fraction: -terpinolene, α -terpinene, ²(+)-limonene.

EXPERIMENTAL

The procedures followed for carrying out the reactions were the same as described earlier. Table I records the pertinent details and references. The analytical methods were similar to those applied before⁴ unless otherwise stated. The results obtained in this study are summarised in Table II.

DISCUSSION

Our first aim was to find out whether (+)-limonene reacted with maleic anhydride under the very mild conditions in which α -terpinene suffered diene reaction, viz., by 4-day keeping of the reactants at room temperature (Reaction a)⁵. As expected, (+)-limonene was recovered unchanged according to its b.p., refractive index, and infrared spectrum. The reaction permits us to extract α -terpinene in admixture with (+)-limonene⁶⁻⁷ as the adduct, which itself serves as a derivative, leaving intact the (+)-limonene for further examination.

Alder and Schmidt's reaction was studied next (Reaction b). In harmony with the finding of Eschinazi and Pines⁸, when a mixture of purified (+)-limonene, maleic anhydride, hydroquinone, and benzene was refluxed for 3 hours, no adduct formed.

To obtain additional information, several runs (c-f) were made, maintaining (+)-limonene: maleic anhydride ratio 1:2. While at room temperature, no change occurred; at $75^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$ stepwise migration of the exterior double bond in (+)-limonene afforded terpinolene and α -terpinene and aromatisation, *p*-cymene (Reactions c, d, e). α -Terpinene was identified by preparing the nitrosite of m.p. 155° . Neither the maleic anhydride nor the maleic acid addition product, corresponding to the conjugated diene, could be isolated. Thus one of the factors that control the behaviour of (+)-limonene towards maleic anhydride is the reaction temperature. As shown by run (b) wherein the reaction temperature was as high as $105-108^{\circ}$ but (+)-limonene: maleic anhydride ratio was ca 3:1, the terpene failed to react. From this we can infer that concentration of maleic anhydride is also responsible in initiating and directing the reaction paths.

It is rather interesting that α -terpinene in spite of surplus dienophile survived 1:4 addition (Reactions c-e). This can only be explained by taking into consideration that α -terpinene is the terminal product in the isomerisation sequence (*vide infra*) and that conditions are unfavourable for its formation of an adduct.

One-hour reaction between (+)-limonene and maleic anhydride in acetone solution, followed by evaporation of the solvent from boiling water bath, provided striking results (Reaction f). This processing brought about isomerisation, aromatisation, and diene reaction, resulting respectively in terpinolene, *p*-cymene, and α -terpinene-maleic anhydride adduct, the adduct being recognised as the maleic acid derivative, following the procedure of Ipatieff and Pines⁸. No free α -terpinene could be detected by nitrosite test. This clearly shows the importance of solvent effect on the course of the reaction.

4. Sugathan and Verghese, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 91.

5. Rudakov *et al.*, *Zhur. Obs. Khim.*, 1954, 24, 1452.

6. Cf. Henry and Paget, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 25.

7. Verghese and Samson, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18, 41.

8. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1120.

From the foregoing data it follows that great caution should be exercised in utilising the reaction with maleic anhydride at 75°⁷ or in acetone medium⁸ for the purpose of detection, estimation, and elimination of conjugated dienes in oils. It is not only oxygenated compounds⁹ but several hydrocarbons of the general formula C₁₀H₁₆ that suffer changes in presence of maleic anhydride under these conditions (unpublished results).

In considering the runs involving the refluxing (155-270°) of a mixture of equimolecular proportions of (+)-limonene and maleic anhydride for 6 and 3 hours (Reactions g and h), the only isomer that could be recognised in the 6-hour reaction was α -terpinene. A significant observation was that terpinolene could not be traced. In contrast to this, in the 3-hour run meagre amounts of terpinolene were also present in the reaction mixture. Thus depending on the reaction period, the nature and distribution of the isomers vary. Under milder conditions (Reactions c,d,e), (+)-limonene, terpinolene, and α -terpinene co-exist and this implies necessity of an isomerisation sequence of the type:

We can therefore conclude that here the initially formed terpinolene is further transformed to the more stable *p*-menthadiene, α -terpinone¹⁰, which is in conformity with the earlier observation that a double bond, exocyclic to a 6-ring, is labile and would wander into the ring^{11,12}.

Finally, we have to account for the formation of *p*-cymene. Reactions (g and h) have provided us the evidence that this aromatic arises by expulsion of succinic anhydride from the maleic anhydride adduct of α -terpinene and/or of other *p*-menthadienes represented schematically by the reaction^{13,14}:

Under milder reaction conditions, however, presumably *p*-cymene is obtained primarily as a consequence of hydrogen-transfer reactions of the type¹⁴:

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13. Littmann, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 586; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1936, 28, 1150.
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